

Causes and Regulatory Mechanism of the Knee Adduction Moment: contributing to explain the medial knee osteoarthritis

Zhijin Xie

Orthopedics, Chengdu No. 7 People's Hospital, No. 1 Twelfth Middle Street, Wuhou District , Chengdu, China. 610021

Abstract

The knee adduction moment (KAM) has been considered closely related to the medial knee osteoarthritis in occurrence and development, until now, it seems that the mechanism of KAM generation has been not clear, and the current researches cannot explain some phenomena well, this article addressed the process of KAM production from the perspective of biomechanics, clarified the reasonable meaning of KAM, explored the joint regulation mechanism of subtalar joint (STJ) and knee, established an internal connection between the regulation mechanism and the KAM, and reasonably explained some clinical phenomena through these discussions. The author believes that a reasonable degree of KAM has benefit for the stability of center of gravity (CG) of the human body and gait propulsion, KAM has corresponding influencing factors and regulatory mechanism too, changes of the STJ and a great amount of soft tissues play positive roles in the regulatory mechanism, correspondingly, function weakening of soft tissue may be the most important biomechanical cause of the medial knee osteoarthritis.

Keywords

Knee adduction moment, Subtalar joint, Knee osteoarthritis, Biomechanics, Mechanism

Introduction

Osteoarthritis of the knee increases in prevalence with age,¹ in which the medial knee osteoarthritis tends to be more common,²⁻⁴ up till now, the known causes of diseases include: gender, age, genetics, obesity, previous knee injury, occupation, sports, knee extensor muscle weakness, knee malalignment, etc.⁵ however, the decisive factor among them was unsure, at present, the mainstream view believes that the medial knee osteoarthritis is closely related to KAM,^{4,6-9} meanwhile, the KAM was also found to be more significant in patients with medial knee osteoarthritis than healthy testers.¹⁰⁻¹² Therefore, to figure out the causes of KAM, the significance of KAM, and the regulatory mechanism of KAM, will be decisive for prevention and treatment of medial knee osteoarthritis.

The generation mechanism of the KAM

The cause concerning the KAM is currently unclear,¹³ Matziolis believe that it is

precisely because the medial knee is closer to the CG that the KAM is generated,¹⁴ while Jackson et al. described it as this way: the KAM results from the combination of the force acting at the foot during gait (which most commonly passes medial to the center of the knee joint) and the distance that this force acts from the center of the knee joint (the lever arm).¹⁵ But the above description does not seem to help much to explain the following phenomenon: usually, the posterolateral heel is firstly worn, and ankle sprains often occur on the lateral,¹⁶ at the same time, ankle osteoarthritis often occurs on the medial side.¹⁷

The explanation below seems to more intuitively explain the origin of KAM: when walking on a normal level, since the CG is basically stable on the coronary axis, the CG is always at inner side of the centre of pressure(COP, can be defined as the center of all the external forces acting on the plantar surface of the foot),¹⁸ at one instant in the stance phase, the resultant force F from the CG to the COP can be decomposed into vertical component force F_1 and horizontal component force F_2 on the coronal plane(Figure 1), and the magnitude of the two component forces will continuously change during continuous walking, the horizontal component force F_2 does not actually cause the CG to swing on the coronary axis, rather against the ground friction when braking, ground friction has a horizontal component force f pointing to the inside of the human body, which causes the KAM.

Figure 1. The decomposition of the resultant force from the CG to the COP.

At one instant in the stance phase, the resultant force F from the center of gravity (CG) to the centre of pressure (COP) can be decomposed into vertical component force F_1 and horizontal component force F_2 on the coronal plane, meanwhile, the ground friction has a horizontal component force f pointing to the inside of the human body, f is opposite to F_2 and has the same size, so it will not cause the center of gravity to swing on the coronary axis, and thus formed the knee adduction moment (KAM).

In the early-stance, after the weight-bearing of heels, part of the ground reaction force causes the CG to be lifted and converted into gravity potential energy,¹⁰ meanwhile, another part of ground reaction force may transform to elastic energy (energy storage process) through deformations of muscles, ligaments, articular cartilage and other structures (may even include bones),¹⁹ elastic energy in this stage can be widely distributed in the above structures, and stress increased in the medial compartment of knee, the medial malleolus and the medial hip joint due to adduction

tendency, however, the soft tissue, including dynamic structures (such as the gluteus minimus, gluteus medius, tensor fasciae latae, vastus lateralis, biceps femoris, peroneus, etc.) and static structures (such as iliotibial tract, lateral collateral ligament, lateral malleolus ligament, etc.) all together can create tension to keep the lower-extremity stable; in the middle-stance, deformation of the arch occurs after further load on the foot, and part of the ground reaction force was converted into the arch elastic energy (energy storage process); but in the late-stance, with the lifting of the heel load, the above-mentioned elastic energy stored in each structure will be released through limb recovery, and converted into kinetic energy to maintain the height and advance of the CG (energy release process).

The process of KAM generation can actually be regarded as “effect of pole vault (EPV)”, just like the kinetic energy generated by a run-up in a pole vault is converted to elastic energy by bending the pole(Figure 2), “ EPV ” can actually cause adduction moment to be present throughout the lower-extremity, not just in knee joint, but the stress most concentrated at knee joint. The stage where the pole releases elastic energy by restoring its original form can improve athletes' CG and get advance, while the Late-stance's lower-extremity deformation process is similar to it, at this stage, both the abduction angles of the hip and knee joints are restored,²⁰ the release of elastic energy can push CG forward and maintain the height of the CG.

Figure 2. About the “ effect of pole vault (EPV) ” .
 In the pole vault, athletes generate kinetic energy through run-ups, after the lower end of the pole is braked by the slot, the kinetic energy of the body can bend the pole, and then convert kinetic energy into elastic energy through pole bending. Subsequently, by restoring the original form, the pole can convert elastic energy into kinetic energy

Significance of the KAM

Multiple studies confirm that healthy people also have KAM,^{10,11,21,22} healthy subjects have been found that their articular cartilage thickness is positively correlated with KAM, and which is thicker on medial femoral condyle,^{23,24} these studies suggest that the presence of KAM is a normal phenomenon, through the foregoing analysis, we should know that: the existence of KAM on the one hand is necessary to maintain CG stability, on the other hand, we can get reasonable elastic energy through proper limb

deformation in gait, and in the propulsion phase converted elastic energy into kinetic energy, which will not only save energy, but also increase human comfort in gait.

Keep the CG stable

In the initial-stance, as the plantar heel begins to bear weight, “EPV” begins to emerge, generates KAM and puts stress on the lateral heel. In the whole process of early-stance, for normal gait, the weight-bearing area gradually increases from back to front on the lateral margin of the sole, eventually reaches the forefoot, during this process, the lower-extremity not only needs to raise the height of CG, but also are accompanied by gradual enhancement of the “EPV”, there is a reality that must be noticed at this time, the CG with initial velocity needs to maintain stability on the coronal axis while being raised in height, at this stage, the weight-bearing path of the sole should follow a curve related to pace and step width(Figure 3), but when the CG pass over the COP, if a person still enter into the middle-stance based on this trend, then the CG will shift to the opposite side during the propulsion phase, which will definitely lead to CG instability, this reduces the walking comfort and increases the energy consumption, therefore, in order to maintain CG stability, the human body must make some adjustments, the author believes that these adjustments include two aspects, STJ’s changes and knee activity of varus & valgus.

Figure 3 : Schematic diagram of the change in the weight-bearing path of the sole during the gait. The solid line predicts the weight-bearing path for normal gait, the dotted line predicts of weight-bearing path without adjustment by ankle-subtalar joint complex (ASTC) and knee joint linkage mechanism, the two differ at the inflection point .

Through a one-foot balance test, we can understand intuitively how the STJ’s changes and knee activity of varus & valgus can stabilize CG on the coronal plane under load, when a person stands on one foot and reaches a steady state, the body will lean towards the side of the weight-bearing limb, and the vertical line of CG coincide with the COP, as the CG moves, the body will change the spatial position of the talus and perform knee varus or valgus, through muscle regulation,²⁵ finally realize the stability of CG. For example: if the CG moves in, the body will tend to fall

inward, accompany the increasing of KAM (due to the increase of F2), the talus will now be adjusted immediately to pronation and plantarflexion,²⁵ that will lead to two results, one is abduction moment generated at the STJ, another is that weight-bearing changes from the heel and entire forefoot to heel and medial forefoot,²⁶ at the same time, knee valgus can be exacerbated probably by strengthening the contraction of the biceps femoris and vastus lateralis (specific instructions shown below),²⁷ which also cause two results, one is the decreasing of KAM, another is the position of knee will be relatively shifted inwards, the linkage mechanism of the two can promote the relative shift of the CG outwards, which can balance the moment and stabilizes the CG; if these adjustments are appropriate, the weight-bearing area will change back to the heel and the entire forefoot, the femorotibial angle will return to the initial position, and the moment will reach equilibrium again, the CG will return to steady state as well; if the adjustment is out of range, the CG will move outside, at that time, the body will tend to fall outward, as KAM is decreasing, the talus will be adjusted again with supination and dorsiflexion,²⁵ which has two effects, one is to generate adduction moment in the STJ, another is to change the weight-bearing from the heel and the entire forefoot to the heel and the lateral forefoot,²⁶ meanwhile, probably by strengthening the semitendinosus, semimembranosus, and gracilis's contractions causes knee varus (sartorius may only be involved when knees are bent), which have two effects, one is the increasing of KAM, another is the relatively shift of knee position outwards, the linkage mechanism of the two factors can promote the relative inward movement of the CG, which achieves the moment balance and the CG stability. The above process of stabilizing CG is like using a fingertip to stabilize an upright club, if the club is about to fall to one side, then by moderately moving the finger to the same side, the club can be stabilized again, in contrast, the stability mechanism of CG is more complicated. The following conclusions can be reached through this experiment: the CG offset from the COP on the coronal axis can cause CG instability, which causes changes in knee joint moment, and the body can balance the lower-extremity moment and maintain the CG stability by actively adjusting the STJ's activity and knee varus or valgus, this adjustment is also controllable within a certain range, the special structure of STJ shows its greatest physiological significance in this adjustment mechanism.

The activities of the STJ

The talus has a special anatomical shape, the upper part of the talar body and the distal tibiofibula form the ginglymus joint together, the displacement of the talus was restrained by the medial and lateral ankles, which, however, allows foot to do dorsiflexion and plantarflexion on sagittal plane, the STJ as a peculiar single anatomo-functional entity due to its connections with the tibiotalar and Chopart's joint and the peculiar anatomical features of the talus in which forces are transmitted to structures above and below.²⁸ The spatial position of the talus will not change unless it bears weight,²⁹ different spatial position changes of talus will produce corresponding moments, and the magnitude and direction of the moments are determined by the position of CG.

Now, the author explains the activities of STJ from a new perspective: the calf and foot are connected as a whole by the ankle and the STJ, which can be called ankle-subtalar joint complex(ASTC), the ASTC can perform a smaller range of varus or valgus activities on the coronal plane, in the initial-stance, the heel stops due to ground friction, the horizontal component force F_2 from CG to the weight-bearing point will cause the distal tibia, talus and upper calcaneus to move outward, however, due to the ground frictional force on the heel, it has a horizontal component force f pointing to the inside of the body, and this pair of force couples will cause the varus of ASTC to form "EPV", increasing the stress of medial ASTC, at the same time, the ankle joint maintains "EPV" by keeping tension of lateral ligament, the knee joint varus and the KAM increased under the action of "EPV", the ASTC activity and knee varus at this stage are mainly passive adjustments(Figure 4-a). As the gait progresses, when the CG passes over the COP (it can be called "inflection point"), STJ will be adjusted due to the need for a stable CG,^{20,30} because the talus has no muscle attachment, it cannot actively change the spatial position, but this change can only be achieved by changing the relative position of adjacent bones and their magnitude of stress, the role of the talus at this time is similar to that of the head when the player holds the ball on top of the head and keeps the ball from falling, the head is only responsible for touching the ball, but the movement is controlled by the neck. A process similar to it is probably mainly through the tensioning regulation of multiple agonist-antagonist muscles such as fibula longus and tibialis posterior, the direction of movement of the tarsal and the amount of force applied to the talus are adjusted, the calcaneus also flipped,²⁵ which indirectly changes the spatial position of the talus, thus, realizes the changes of the ASTC moment and the plantar eight-bearing mode, accompanying with knee valgus linkage changes,²⁰ these changes can stabilize CG, and ensure that the CG does not shift during the propulsion phase, during this adjustment, the weight-bearing path of the sole will no longer follow the lateral path before the inflection point, but gradually inward and forward, leading to the weight-bearing of the whole forefoot (Figure 3), the KAM is reduced at this time, the tension of the internal and external ankle ligament is basically balanced, at this stage the ASTC activity and knee valgus are belong to active regulation (Figure 4-b). There is also a condition that causes the medial malleolus ligament to be tense and the lateral malleolus ligament to be loose, when a person is standing on one foot, if the CG moves inward, the talus can produce greater pronation and plantarflexion than during the propulsion phase under the corresponding agonist-antagonist muscles strengthening activities, which results in a greater abduction moment at the ASTC, this balances the increased KAM caused by the CG inward movement, meanwhile, there will also be more pronounced valgus linkage changes in the knee joint, at this stage, the ASTC activity and knee valgus are also active adjustments (Figure 4-c), patients with medial knee osteoarthritis show more pronounced pronation type for the same reason.³¹ It can be found from the above analysis that the change of moment not only occurs in SJT, but more accurately, the changes in STJ and ankle joint are synchronized to produce the moment's change, which is the reason why the author uses the name "ankle-subtalar joint complex" here.

Figure 4: Varus or valgus of ASTC in different states.

a: Shown in the initial-stance, varus of ASTC due to “EPV”, at this time, the lateral malleolus ligament remains tense.

b: Shown in the middle-stance, in order to stabilize the CG, ASTC has been adjusted to the center position. at this time, the tension of the medial and lateral ligaments is basically the same.

c: Shown when the CG moves in, ASTC was adjusted to valgus, in order to balance the moment and stabilize CG, and the medial malleolus ligament remains tense at this time.

It should be noted that changes in the spatial position of the talus do not necessarily begin after the forefoot has been loaded, because this will cause excess energy consumption and CG instability, accordingly, forefoot weight-bearing is not a necessary condition for the change of talar spatial position, at the same time, nor is the talar spatial position determining the muscle activity of the lower-extremity, but the opposite, that will be a challenge to what we already know.^{25,26,29,32} The inflection point can appear sooner or later, it is dynamically adjusted according to the balance needs of CG, the author believes that all activities in gait must simultaneously take into account CG’s stability. Moreover, the talar spatial position was not actively adjusted before the inflection point appeared, the author believes that the greatest possibility is that - this Tai Chi-style homeopath will be more energy-saving and more comfortable for the human body. Surely, this analysis also needs to be supported by corresponding biomechanical tests.

In fact, with the change in the talar spatial position, the foot has another important function, accompanied by pronation and plantarflexion of talus, it reduced medial longitudinal arch height, the first metatarsal will be descending and advancing,²⁵ and the transverse arch sinks, matching these bony structural changes is the extension of the soft tissue such as the masses of muscles, tendons, and ligaments, increased tension, this is a process in which the arch of the foot acts as a buffer, it is

also the process of converting the gravitational potential energy into elastic energy,³³ at this time, the stored elastic energy in the arch will be transformed into the driving force in the propulsion phase.

The author understand the source of the double peaks in the KAM waveform as following: in the early-stance, “EPV” formed after heel weight-bearing will cause early-stance KAM, the early-stance peak KAM appears when the CG passes over the COP, subsequently, F2 gradually decreases as CG moves forward, in order to stabilize CG, ASTC activity and knee valgus adjustment will also occur, the KAM gradually decreases, but after entering into the middle-stance, the contralateral lower-extremity entered into the swing phase, therefore, the KAM does not completely disappear during weight-bearing alone, once entering into the late-stance, with the heel off the ground, the elastic energy forms in the early stages of the weight-bearing limbs begins to release, forming a late-stance KAM under the combined effect with the triceps of the calf.

The above explanation can be used to explain the author's question at the beginning of the article: the posterolateral heel is worn first because the stress is most concentrated here, in the initial-stance; lateral ankle sprains are more common, because the “EPV” causes the ASTC varus in the early-stance, the lateral malleolus ligament has high tension, and the weight-bearing part of the foot is incomplete at this stage, the stability of ankle would be the worst, at the same time, the STJ's activity is still in the passive adjustment stage, which is responsible for adjusting STJ's agonist muscles tension is insufficient, it is difficult to make timely adjustment in case of ground accidents; ankle osteoarthritis often occurs on the medial side because in the early-stance, stress is concentrated in the medial ankle compartment,³⁴ however, the medial and lateral ankle compartments were almost equally stressed in the middle-stance and late-stance.

Influencing factors and regulatory mechanism of KAM

Based on the previous discussion, it can be found that in normal gait, the generation of KAM is inevitable, but KAM is not constant and changes constantly due to some factors in gait. The author divides the factors that can affect the size of KAM into controllable and uncontrollable factors, for example, pace, step width, and toe-out angle are controllable factors, while weight, femorotibial angle, muscle strength, and ligament tension are uncontrollable factors. Reasonable adjustment of controllable factors may help to reduce KAM to a certain extent, but such adjustments often bring about associated changes in motor system, so these adjustments may only be expedient, and changes of uncontrollable factors are the basis for changes in KAM, therefore, adjustments to changes in uncontrollable factors are the key to reverse the situation. Methods such as arthroscopy can neither change the controllable factors that affect KAM, nor change the uncontrollable factors, so it is difficult to affect the progress of medial knee osteoarthritis.³⁵

Regulating KAM through gait adjustment

It is generally believed that decreasing the pace may reduce KAM, but it is not necessarily, decreasing the pace can be achieved by decreasing the step length or frequency : decreasing the step length can reduce CG fluctuation and reduce the resultant force on the tibial plateau when the CG passes over the COP; simply reducing the step frequency will destroy the continuous movement of the CG, and the CG fluctuations will increase instead, in addition, in these two different methods of speed reduction, the exerting force of the limb during the propulsion phase is also different, for example, only decreasing the step frequency would lead to unreasonable release of elastic energy, and more force must be applied to push CG during propulsion phase, which would cause the change of KAM, if these actions are not accurately restricted, the change of KAM will be unpredictable.^{10,12,20-22} The same goes for increasing pace.

Increasing the step width will generally increase the horizontal component force F_2 , and the increase in the lateral swing of CG will also affect the horizontal component force F_2 , resulting in an increase in KAM, however, as the stability of the body decreases, the active increase of ASTC activity and knee valgus regulation are also enhanced, which will cause the KAM to decrease, so it will be difficult to estimate the results without making accurate limits.^{36,37} Reducing the step width is quite special, on the one hand, F_2 can be reduced by approaching the CG on the coronary axis with the COP, on the other hand, as the step width decreases, the ASTC valgus occurs, the resulting ASTC's abduction moment needs to increase KAM to maintain the CG's stability, otherwise, the CG will swing inward, so the effect of reducing the step width on KAM is also uncertain.³⁸

Increasing the toe-out angle is a common gait adjustment method for patients with medial knee osteoarthritis, generally speaking, this autonomous adjustment is beneficial to reduce KAM, but increasing the toe-out angle will shift the task of CG stability on the sagittal axis that should be controlled by the flexion and extension of the ankle joint, STJ will undertake more tasks, and the resulting changes will be more complicated, for example, a slight forward and backward leaning of the body during gait will cause a change in the position of the CG on the sagittal axis, which will cause a linkage reaction between ASTC and knee joint, thereby causing changes in KAM, changes in muscle tone of the lower-extremity can also affect ASTC and knee joint activity, and usually maintaining moderate tension will be more conducive to the reduction of KAM, however, this regulation mechanism is very complicated, and it is difficult to accurately limit each condition in the experiment, which will lead to the research results not being uniform, or even opposing.^{37,39,40} A small decrease in the toe-out angle may not have a meaningful impact on KAM, and a significant decrease in the toe-out angle may increase KAM.^{40,41}

In short, there are many ways to reduce KAM by adjusting the gait, but the factors that affect the gait are very complicated, small changes may cause differences in results, due to limited space, this content can be discussed more in subsequent articles.

The influence of uncontrollable factors on KAM

The effect of weight on KAM is direct, decreasing weight can reduce the horizontal component force F_2 and thus reduce KAM,⁴² while increasing weight is the opposite.²⁰

If only from the perspective of physics, there is no doubt that the femorotibial angle will directly affect the size of KAM,⁴³ the method of reducing the femorotibial angle can reduce KAM, reasonable overcorrection can make the Mikulicz line under the influence of “EPV” more centered instead of shifted inward, thereby making the long-term effect better.⁴³⁻⁴⁶ However, it must be noted that in theory, there should be a matching soft tissue balance for the basic femorotibial angles of each individual after development, for example, if a child with rickets has a varus of the knee, the soft tissue that controls the KAM in his body is likely to be more developed than normal in adulthood, therefore, it seems unreasonable to judge the size of KAM directly from the size of femorotibial angle.

The use of lateral wedge soles in theory can only work before the inflection point (the passive adjustment phase of ASTC and knee joints), once the body enters the active regulation stage in order to stabilize CG, the lateral wedge sole will no longer play a role in reducing KAM, this is why the lateral wedge sole can reduce the early-stance KAM, but not the subsequent phase KAM.⁴⁷ The use of lateral wedge soles alone will not reduce the femorotibial angle, because the increased ASTC valgus moment must be counteracted by other increased varus moments so that the CG can be balanced, while the use of a novel strapped insole will increase knee valgus activity due to restricting the ASTC activity, so KAM can be reduced by reducing the femorotibial angle,⁴⁸ however, this method will inevitably bring about a decrease in gait comfort and an increase in energy consumption.

The “EPV” requires the tension of the soft tissue to maintain, theoretically, the function decline of dynamic soft tissue of lower-extremity caused by any reason, for example, muscle atrophy or weakness caused by reduced activity, disuse, or neuromuscular disease may reduce the body's ability to actively control “EPV”, and affect lower-extremity stability, leading to increased KAM, therefore, for the increasing trend of KAM, the body must actively increase muscle activity to slow down its development,⁴⁹ and physical exercise has been proved to be effective in relieving pain and improving function of patients with osteoarthritis.⁵⁰ Patients with knee osteoarthritis were observed to have an increase in KAM after taking anti-inflammatory drugs, while KAM tended to decrease without anti-inflammatory drugs,⁵¹ this phenomenon is precisely a manifestation of controlling KAM through muscle strength.

The static soft tissue that has the greatest impact on KAM should be the iliotibial tract, this physiological structure has not been found in other predators,⁵² why is it owned by humans? Yount observes that iliotibial tract contracture in polio patients can cause tibial eversion,⁵³ Beals also pointed out that when amputation above the knee joint, hip abduction contracture may occur if the iliotibial tract is fixed to the femur,⁵⁴ the above observations support the iliotibial tract as an important stable structure of the lower-extremity of the human body, and it can be deduced from this that the iliotibial tract has the effect of limiting knee varus, therefore, the iliotibial

tract may be extremely important for controlling KAM. Anatomically, the iliotibial tract is formed by the coalescence of fascial investments of the tensor fascia femoris, the gluteus maximus, and the gluteus medius,⁵⁵ it extends downward after passing through the trochanter's shallow surface, ending at the Gerdy's tubercle, biomechanical studies prove that the iliotibial tract is strong enough to provide anterolateral stability to the tibia,^{55,56} therefore, it is likely that such a mechanism exists : in the stance phase, through the joint action of gluteus minimus, gluteus medius and lateral femoral muscle, the femur is rotated internally, resulting in an increase of offset of hip, in this way, the tension of iliotibial tract will increase, in this way, the tension of the iliotibial tract will be increased, and in addition to the strengthening effect of the above muscles after tightening, ^{27,57} the iliotibial tract will act as a tension band, which can both stabilize the hip joint and limit knee varus (Figure 5) . The study found that simultaneous hip abductor and quadriceps muscle strength training can improve the pain, function and quality of life of patients with knee OA earlier than the quadriceps muscle strength training alone, ⁵⁸ which is the strong support for the above hypothetical mechanism. Brouwer et al. found that during the one-year follow-up period, closed wedge osteotomy had fewer loss angles than open wedge osteotomy for medial knee osteoarthritis,⁵⁹ this may be because the open wedge osteotomy reduces the tension of the iliotibial tract, and it is not possible to make adaptive changes in the short term after surgery to achieve the optimal tension of the iliotibial tract, the closed wedge osteotomy may increase the tension of the iliotibial tract, thereby restoring the role of the iliotibial tract in limiting varus. The author believes that the weakening of the iliotibial tract for a tension band may also be an important biomechanical factor in the generation of medial knee osteoarthritis.

Figure 5: The iliotibial tract acts as a tension band. In stance phase, femur pronates under the joint action of gluteus minimus, gluteus medius and lateral femoral muscle, the tension of iliotibial tract is increased, which can act as a tension band, at the same time, the muscles become thick and hard after contraction, and can also strengthen the action of tension band, which can stabilize the hip joint and limit genu varum.

Conclusion

knee osteoarthritis is a leading contributor to disability worldwide,⁶⁰ the medial knee osteoarthritis is the most common type, it is significant to find out the pathogenesis of the disease. Through basic biomechanical analysis, the author gives a reasonable explanation to the mechanism of KAM generation and the role of elastic energy in gait, and expounds the importance of this mechanism for CG stability, gait comfort and energy saving. Furthermore, the author also put forward the hypothesis of a linkage regulation mechanism between STJ and the knee joint, which establishes an internal connection with the change of KAM, and thus deduces the factors that can affect the change of KAM and its regulation mechanism. Through the above constructive discussion, the author believes that: the cause of medial knee osteoarthritis is mainly due to the weakening of the soft tissue structure of the lower-extremity, or the relatively weakening of the soft tissue structure of the lower-extremity caused by weight gain, proper adjustment of gait or use of assistive devices may help reduce the progress of medial knee osteoarthritis, but all adjustment methods may lead to reduced gait comfort and increased energy consumption. Being lack of the support of relevant biomechanical tests, part of the viewpoints needs further research to prove.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank Dr. Shuo Ji for helpful discussion.

References

- 1.Felson DT. Clinical practice. Osteoarthritis of the knee. *N Engl J Med*. 2006; **354**(8): 841-848.
- 2.Ledingham J, Regan M, Jones A, et al. Radiographic patterns and associations of osteoarthritis of the knee in patients referred to hospital. *Ann Rheum Dis*. 1993; **52**(7): 520-526.
- 3.Mündermann A, Dyrby CO, Andriacchi TP. Secondary gait changes in patients with medial compartment knee osteoarthritis: Increased load at the ankle, knee, and hip during walking. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2005; **52**(9): 2835-2844.
- 4.Birmingham TB, Hunt MA, Jones IC, et al. Test-retest reliability of the peak knee adduction moment during walking in patients with medial compartment knee Osteoarthritis. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2007; **57** (6): 1012-1017.
- 5.Hunter DJ, Bierma-Zeinstra S. Osteoarthritis. *Lancet*. 2019; **393**(10182): 1745-1759.
- 6.Asay JL, Erhart-Hledik JC, Andriacchi TP. Changes in the Total Knee Joint Moment in Patients with Medial Compartment Knee Osteoarthritis over Five Years. *J Orthop Res*. 2018; **36**(9): 2373-2379.
- 7.Zhao D, Banks SA, Mitchell KH, et al. Correlation between the knee adduction torque and medial contact force for a variety of gait patterns. *J Orthop Res*. 2007; **25**(6): 789-797.
- 8.Simic M, Hinman RS, Wrigley TV, et al. Gait modification strategies for altering medial knee joint load: A systematic review. *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken)* 2011;

63(3): 405-426.

9.van den Noort JJ, van der Esch M, Steultjens MP, et al. Ambulatory measurement of the knee adduction moment in patients with osteoarthritis of the knee. *J Biomech.* 2013; **46**(1): 43-49.

10.Mündermann A, Dyrby CO, Hurwitz DE, et al. Potential Strategies to Reduce Medial Compartment Loading in Patients With Knee Osteoarthritis of Varying Severity: Reduced Walking Speed. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2004; **50**(4): 1172-1178.

11.Baliunas AJ, Hurwitz DE, Ryals AB, et al. Increased knee joint loads during walking are present in subjects with knee osteoarthritis. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage.* 2002; **10**(7): 573-579.

12.Zeni JA Jr, Higginson JS. Differences in gait parameters between healthy subjects and persons with moderate and severe knee osteoarthritis: A result of altered walking speed?. *Clin Biomech (Bristol, Avon).* 2009; **24**(4): 372-378.

13.Creaby MW. It's not all about the knee adduction moment: the role of the knee flexion moment in medial knee joint loading. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage.* 2015; **23**(7): 1038-1040.

14.Matziolis G, Röhner E. [Arthritis of the Medial Knee Joint Compartment]. *Z Orthop Unfall.* 2015; **153**(5): 553-564.

15.Jackson BD, Wluka AE, Teichtahl AJ, et al. Reviewing knee osteoarthritis--a biomechanical perspective. *J Sci Med Sport.* 2004; **7**(3): 347-357.

16.Fallat L, Grimm DJ, Saracco JA. Sprained ankle syndrome: Prevalence and analysis of 639 acute injuries. *J Foot Ankle Surg.* 1998; **37**(4): 280-285.

17.Muehleman C, Bareither D, Huch K, et al. Prevalence of degenerative morphologic changes in the joints of the lower extremity. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage* 1997; **5**(1): 23-37.

18.Karia M, Masjedi M, Duffell L, et al. Comparison of gait biomechanics in patients with and without knee osteoarthritis during different phases of gait. *J Orthop Trauma Rehabil.* 2018; **25**(2): 11-15.

19.Simonsen EB. Contributions to the understanding of gait control. *Dan Med J.* 2014; **61**(4): B4823.

20.Shultz SP, Sitler MR, Tierney RT, et al. Effects of Pediatric Obesity on Joint Kinematics and Kinetics During 2 Walking Cadences. *Arch Phys Med Rehab.* 2009; **90**(12): 2146-2154.

21.Robbins SM, Maly MR. The effect of gait speed on the knee adduction moment depends on waveform summary measures. *Gait Posture.* 2009; **30**(4): 543-546.

22.McClelland JA, Webster KE, Feller JA, et al. Knee kinetics during walking at different speeds in people who have undergone total knee replacement. *Gait Posture.* 2010; **32**(2): 205-210.

23.Chaudhari AM, Briant PL, Bevill SL, et al. Knee Kinematics, Cartilage Morphology, and Osteoarthritis after ACL Injury. *Med Sci Sports Exerc.* 2008; **40**(2): 215-522.

24.Andriacchi TP, Mündermann A, Smith RL, et al. A framework for the in vivo pathomechanics of osteoarthritis at the knee. *Ann Biomed Eng.* 2004; **32**(3): 447-457.

25.Kirby KA. Rotational equilibrium across the subtalar joint axis. *J Am Podiatr Med*

Assoc. 1989; **79**(1): 1-14.

26.Kirby KA. Subtalar Joint Axis Location and Rotational Equilibrium Theory of Foot Function. *J Am Podiatr Med Assoc.* 2001; **91**(9): 465-487.

27.Plewa K, Samadani A, Chau T. Comparing electro- and mechano-myographic muscle activation patterns in self-paced pediatric gait. *J Electromyogr Kines.* 2017; **36**: 73-80.

28.Palma LD, Santucci A, Ventura A, et al. Anatomy and embryology of the talocalcaneal joint. *Foot Ankle Surg.* 2003; **9**(1): 7-18.

29.Lear dini A, Stagni R, O'Connor JJ. Mobility of the subtalar joint in the intact ankle complex. *J Biomech.* 2001; **34**(6): 805-809.

30.Hunt AE, Smith RM, Torode M, et al. Inter-segment foot motion and ground reaction forces over the stance phase of walking. *Clin Biomech.* 2001; **16**(7): 592-600.

31.Levinger P, Menz HB, Fotoohabadi MR, et al. Foot posture in people with medial compartment knee osteoarthritis. *J Foot Ankle Surg.* 2010; **3**: 29.

32.Lewis GS, Kirby KA, Piazza SJ. Determination of subtalar joint axis location by restriction of talocrural joint motion. *Gait Posture.* 2007; **25**(1): 63-69.

33.Kelly LA, Farris DJ, Cresswell AG, et al. Intrinsic foot muscles contribute to elastic energy storage and return in the human foot. *J Appl Physiol.* 2019; **126**(1): 231-238.

34.Valderrabano V, Horisberger M, Russell I, et al. Etiology of ankle osteoarthritis. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2009; **467**(7): 1800-1806.

35.Kirkley A, Birmingham TB, Litchfield RB, et al. A Randomized Trial of Arthroscopic Surgery for Osteoarthritis of the Knee. *N Engl J Med.* 2008; **359**(11): 1097-1107.

36.Fregly BJ, Reinbolt JA, Chmielewski TL. Evaluation of a patient-specific cost function to predict the influence of foot path on the knee adduction torque during gait. *Comput Methods Biomech Biomed Engin.* 2008; **11**(1): 63-71.

37.Reinbolt JA, Haftka RT, Chmielewski TL, et al. A computational framework to predict post-treatment outcome for gait-related disorders. *Med Eng Phys.* 2008; **30**(4): 434-443.

38.Street BD, Gage W. The effects of an adopted narrow gait on the external adduction moment at the knee joint during level walking: Evidence of asymmetry. *Hum Movement Sci.* 2013; **32**(2): 301-313.

39.Guo M, Axe MJ, Manal K. The influence of foot progression angle on the knee adduction moment during walking and stair climbing in pain free individuals with knee osteoarthritis. *Gait Posture.* 2007; **26**(3): 436-441.

40.Lin CJ, Lai KA, Chou YL, et al. The effect of changing foot progression angle on the knee adduction moment in normal teenagers. *Gait Posture.* 2001; **14**(2): 85-91.

41.Lynn SK, Kajaks T, Costigan PA. The effect of internal and external foot rotation on the adduction moment and lateral-medial shear force at the knee during gait. *J Sci Med Sport* 2008; **11**(5): 444-451.

42.Astephen Wilson JL, Deluzio KJ, Dunbar MJ, et al. The association between knee joint biomechanics and neuromuscular control and moderate knee osteoarthritis radiographic and pain severity. *Osteoarthr Cartilage.* 2011; **19**(2):186-193.

43. Wada M, Imura S, Nagatani K, et al. Relationship Between Gait and Clinical Results After High Tibial Osteotomy. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 1998; (354): 180-188.
44. Koshino T, Tsuchiya K. The effect of high tibial osteotomy on osteoarthritis of the knee. *Int Orthop.* 1979; **3**(1):37-45.
45. Majima T, Yasuda K, Katsuragi R, et al. Progression of Joint Arthrosis 10 to 15 Years After High Tibial Osteotomy. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2000; (381):177-184.
46. Habata T, Uematsu K, Hattori K, et al. High tibial osteotomy that does not cause recurrence of varus deformity for medial gonarthrosis. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc.* 2006; **14**(10):962-967.
47. Butler RJ, Marchesi S, Royer T, et al. The effect of a subject-specific amount of lateral wedge on knee mechanics in patients with medial knee osteoarthritis. *J Orthop Res.* 2007; **25**(9): 1121-1127.
48. Toda Y, Segal N, Kato A, et al. Effect of a novel insole on the subtalar joint of patients with medial compartment osteoarthritis of the knee. *J Rheumatol.* 2012; **28**(12): 2705-2710.
49. van der Esch M, Steultjens M, Knol DL, et al. Joint laxity and the relationship between muscle strength and functional ability in patients with osteoarthritis of the knee. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2006; **55**(6): 953-959.
50. Gay C, Chabaud A, Guilley E, et al. Educating Patients About the Benefits of Physical Activity and Exercise for Their Hip and Knee Osteoarthritis. Systematic Literature Review. *Ann Phys Rehabil Med.* 2016; **59**(3): 174-183.
51. Hurwitz DE, Ryals AR, Block JA, et al. Knee pain and joint loading in subjects with osteoarthritis of the knee. *J Orthop Res.* 2000; **18**(4): 572-579.
52. Kaplan EB. The iliotibial tract; clinical and morphological significance. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1958; **40**(4): 817-832.
53. Yount CC. The role of the tensor fasciae femoris in certain deformities of the lower extremities. *J Bone Joint Surg.* 1926; **8**: 171-193.
54. Beals RK. The iliotibial tract: a review. *Current Orthopaedic Practice.* 2009; **20**(1): 87-91.
55. Terry GC, Hughston JC, Norwood LA. The anatomy of the iliopatellar band and iliotibial tract. *Am J Sports Med.* 1986; **14**(1): 39-45.
56. Kennedy JC, Stewart R, Walker DM. Anterolateral rotatory instability of the knee joint. An early analysis of the Ellison procedure. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1978; **60**(8): 1031-1039.
57. Saywell N, Taylor D, Boocock M. During step descent, older adults exhibit decreased knee range of motion and increased vastus lateralis muscle activity. *Gait Posture.* 2012; **36**(3): 490-494.
58. Yuenyongviwat V, Duangmanee S, Iamthanaporn K, et al. Effect of hip abductor strengthening exercises in knee osteoarthritis: a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord.* 2020; **21**(1): 284.
59. Brouwer RW, Bierma-Zeinstra SM, van Raaij TM, et al. Osteotomy for medial compartment arthritis of the knee using a closing wedge or an opening wedge controlled by a Puddu plate: A ONE-YEAR RANDOMISED, CONTROLLED STUDY. *J Bone Joint Surg Br.* 2006; **88**(11): 1454-1459.

60. Buchbinder R. Meniscectomy in Patients with Knee Osteoarthritis and a Meniscal Tear?. *N Engl J Med.* 2013; **368**(18): 1740-1741.